

was recrystallised from hot benzene to give light brown crystals of 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone (80%), m.p. 162° (Found: C, 70.02; H, 4.82; N, 4.48. $C_{18}H_{15}NO_4$ calcd. for: C, 69.90; H, 4.85; N, 4.53%).

Reaction with 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-toluidine, 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-anisidine, 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-phenetidine, 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-chloroaniline and 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-bromoaniline was carried out by using the above procedure. The above reactions also resulted in formation of 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone (3) (85-70%).

References

1. A. H. BLATT, *Org. Synth.*, 1961, 2, 55.
2. S. MOHAN, B. KUMAR and J. S. SANDHU, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1971, 671.
3. M. RAI, K. KRISHAN and A. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 847.
4. M. RAI, B. KAUR and B. S. DHIR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 56, 416.

Synthesis of some New Antifungal Tetrazolyl Sulphides

S. K. SANGAL* and ASHOK KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

Manuscript received 1 April 1985, accepted 2 December 1985

A well known fact about 1,2,3,4-tetrazoles is that they have a varied spectrum of biological activities¹. This nucleus when present in a compound imparts anticonvulsant², radio-protective³ and spermatostatic⁴ properties to that compound. The SH group attached to the nucleus may enhance the pharmacological activities⁵. The sulphides have been reported to possess more biological activities than the parent mercapto compounds⁶. Moreover, the heterocyclic disulphides have been known to possess significant antifungal activity⁷. Studies of pesticidal activities of bis(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)alkanes have indicated that activity increased⁸ with the increase in the number of methylene groups. These studies in the modification of pharmacological activities of heterocyclics, prompted the authors to take up the synthesis of new tetrazolyl sulphides and to screen these compounds for their fungicidal activity. As speculated, these compounds have been found to possess significant fungicidal activity.

1-Aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiols (3) have been prepared by the method of Freund and Hempel⁹.

These have been converted to bis-tetrazolyl disulphides (4) and to bis-ethylene disulphides (5) according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Reagents: (i) HNO₃; (ii) aqueous NaOH; (iii) Br₂; C₂H₅OH; (iv) BrCH₂CH₂Br; (v) anhydrous CH₃COONa.

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Their characterisation has been done by ir spectra. Eighteen of the title compounds have been screened for their fungicidal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. Some of these compounds exhibited satisfactory antifungal activity.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer. 5-Aryl-amino-1,2,3,4-thiazotriazoles (2) were prepared by the action of HNO₃ on 1 in cold.

Bis(1-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazol-5-yl)disulphides (4): The compounds were prepared by oxidation of 1-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiol (3) with bromine. To an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 3 (0.01 M), a cold ethanolic solution (20 ml) of bromine (0.01 M) was added dropwise with stirring. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised (Table 1).

Bis(1-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazol-5-yl)ethylene disulphides (5): To an ethanolic solution of 3 (0.01 M), anhydrous sodium acetate and ethylene bromide (0.005 M) were added. The contents were refluxed for 4 to 5 h and then poured into cold water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Fungicidal screening: All the nineteen compounds were evaluated for their fungitoxicity by agar plate technique¹⁰ against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* at three different concentrations, namely 1:1 000 and 1:10 000 and 1:100 000. The number of replications in each was three. The percentage inhibition (after 90 h) by various compounds are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

All the tested compounds possessed significant

TABLE 1—BIS(1-ARYL-1,2,3,4-TETRAZOLYL) DISULPHIDES (4)

Sl. no.	R	M. p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd.)		% Inhibition (1 : 10 000)	
					N	S	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1.	H	184	79.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₈ S ₂	30.9 (31.3)	18.2 (18.0)	57.2	48.5
2.	2-CH ₃	224	69.2	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₈ S ₂ ¹	29.0 (29.3)	16.4 (16.8)	44.6	41.7
3.	4-CH ₃	167	72.2	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₈ S ₂	—	—	38.5	36.3
4. ^a	4-Cl	195	85.3	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	26.0 (26.4)	14.8 (15.2)	50.1	45.8
5.	3-Cl	176	90.2	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	52.4	46.7
6.	2-Cl	200	76.1	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	55.6	53.8
7.	2-OCH ₃	164	86.3	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	26.1 (27.0)	14.8 (15.4)	60.2	58.9
8.	3-OCH ₃ ¹	238	90.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	—	—	57.8	51.2
9.	4-OCH ₃	219	92.2	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ ¹	26.3 (27.0)	14.6 (15.4)	62.9	58.1
10.	2-CH ₃ ,5-Cl	254	80.3	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂ ¹	22.5 (23.1)	12.9 (12.2)	58.7	56.9
11.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	225	87.5	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	24.1 (25.0)	13.7 (14.4)	59.6	56.7
12.	4-NO ₂ ,2-Cl	185	68.9	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₁₀ O ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	28.3 (29.1)	13.0 (13.4)	46.7	44.5
13.	2-NO ₂ ,4-Cl	159	66.5	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₁₀ O ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	51.8	47.5

^aλ_{max} 1 581 (C=N conj.), 736¹(C-S-C) and 759 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).

TABLE 2—BIS(1-ARYL-1,2,3,4-TETRAZOL-5-YL)ETHYLENEDISULPHIDES (5)

Sl. no.	R	M. p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd.)		% Inhibition (1 : 100 000)	
					N	S	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
14.	H	95	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₈ S ₂	28.6 (29.3)	16.1 (16.7)	54.0	49.3
15.	2-OCH ₃	120	61	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	24.7 (25.0)	13.6 (14.4)	59.1	50.9
16.	3-Cl	85	49	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	24.5 (24.8)	14.0 (14.1)	57.2	56.1
17. ^a	4-Cl	115	78	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	53.7	50.5
18.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	66	86	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	22.9 (23.8)	13.1 (13.6)	62.1	55.2
19.	2-NO ₂	76	79	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₁₀ O ₂ S ₂	29.0 (29.6)	12.7 (13.5)	57.5	49.8

^aλ_{max} 1 581 (C=N conj.), 736 (C-S-C) and 759 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).